

MULTI-SCALE MODELING OF FIBER-REINFORCED PLASTIC COMPOSITES: FROM ATOMISTIC MODELING TO STRUCTURAL DESIGN

Tomonaga OKABE

6-6-01, Aoba-yama, Aoba-ku, Sendai, Miyagi, Japan, Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tohoku University, email:okabe@plum.mech.tohoku.ac.jp, website:
<http://www.plum.mech.tohoku.ac.jp/toppage.html>

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ABSTRACT

We have developed numerical modeling of the damage and failure process seen in fibre reinforced composites. Recently, we have tried to expand the modeling and apply it to the structural design of composite components. Such multidisciplinary studies are presently global. This approach is related from the atomistic to structural scale, so that the designer can easily discern the relationship between material properties and structural components. This paper will introduce such a new and comprehensive approach to multi-scale modeling of a fiber-reinforced composite considering bridging of scales. The proposed approach is not always tightly connected in a scheme, and each scale is independently modeled. However, the results from a series of models give us a concise view of how to connect those scales and how to use the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are gaining wide applications in aircraft, spacecraft, automobiles, and energy generation. However, their analysis still presents challenges due to the multiple scales from micro-level to the structural. For example, to analyze the deformation of a composite structure, it should be regarded as an anisotropic body on a macroscopic scale. However, to analyze its failure or damage, one must use microscopic analysis with the representative volume elements (RVEs) considering micro cracks in the matrix and/or at fiber-matrix interfaces. Furthermore, for fabrication and processing, the molecular or atomistic scale at which fiber and resin react also must be considered (i.e., molecular dynamic simulation). This paper will introduce a new and comprehensive approach to multi-scale modeling of a fiber-reinforced composite considering bridging of scales. Figure 1 depicts a schematic diagram of bottom-up multiscale modeling for composite wing structures. At the microscopic scale, the matrix properties of composites are derived from molecular dynamics simulation. The obtained properties are plugged into the micromechanical unit cell simulations, to yield the constitutive law in mesoscopic or structural analyses. This paper will discuss the topics listed in the next section.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of bottom-up multiscale modeling for composite wing structures.

2 RESEARCH TOPICS FROM ATOMISTIC MODELING TO STRUCTURAL DESIGN

2.1 Atomistic simulation of the curing reaction of Epoxy resin [1-2]

The quality of composite products highly depends on the properties of polymer resin as stated above. Recently, we developed a new numerical scheme addressing the molecular structures of epoxy resin. This approach is based on the combination of ab initio quantum mechanics, Monte Carlo chemical simulation, and molecular dynamics simulation. This enables us to directly predict the material properties including CTE, Young's modulus, curing shrinkage, and glass-transition temperature without experiments.

Figure 2 presents our proposed procedure to simulate a cross-link polymer like thermosetting resin. First, the uncured system is set up in the periodic unit cell. Second, those monomers are numerically cured with the help of the Monte Carlo approach, which considers the activation energy estimated by the ab-initio calculation. Using the simulated polymer system, the material properties, including the gelation, the cure shrinkage, and coefficient of thermal expansion, will be estimated by molecular dynamics simulation. We applied our scheme to analyze the curing structures of phenol resin and to obtained the appropriate molecular structures. Figure 3 is a schematic figure of the formation of a polymer network during the computational simulation. It should be noted that this includes the additional and condensational reaction.

Figure 2: Schematic figure of MD simulation for a cross-link polymer like thermosetting resin.

Figure 3: Schematic figure of formation of polymer network during computational simulation.

2.2 Numerical simulation of matrix cracking and fiber breaking in unidirectional carbon-fiber-reinforced composites [3-5]

The cracking onset strain of the transverse ply and the ultimate tensile strength of the longitudinal ply are utilized as the design limits of the composite structural components. Our group has been developing a numerical scheme for predicting these properties. The models have been compared with experiments and validated through the comparisons. In particular, we recently demonstrated that the ultimate tensile strength of the longitudinal ply is highly influenced by the matrix cracks around fiber breaks. Figure 4 illustrates the fragmentation process seen in the multi fiber fragmentation tests. As seen in the figures, the neighboring fibers are broken by the stress concentration due to matrix cracking around fiber breaks. Figure 5 depicts the damage progress seen in the numerical simulation with the spring-element model. The damage pattern is obviously influenced by this stress concentration. The predicted properties can be implemented as the design limits through the tensor form strength formulation as in the Tsai-Wu model.

Figure 4: Fragmentation process seen in the multi fiber fragmentation tests.

Figure 5: Damage progress seen in the numerical simulation with the spring-element model.

2.3 Modeling progressive damage in fiber-reinforced laminates using continuum damage mechanics [6,7]

Substantial transverse cracking may give rise to more deleterious forms of damage, or directly reduce the stiffness of the composite structures. Two approaches to address the damage are shown in Figure 6. One is a direct discrete modeling approach with CZM. The other is a continuous approach that estimates the reduced stiffness with continuum damage mechanics (CDM). This approach utilizes the internal state variable and damage variable to consider the effect of transverse cracks on reducing stiffness. Here, we will introduce the three-dimensional local stress field (3-D LSF) model, which is a refined two-dimensional local stress field model. As shown in Figure 7, the present model is compared to the finite-element results of Gudmundosn et al. A new continuum damage mechanics model, which is an energy-based model of ply cracking of general composite laminates, is presented using the 3-D LSF model and the CDM approach. The damage variable in the direction normal to the fiber was derived for the ply including transverse cracking as a function of transverse crack density using the 3-D LSF model.

	Continuous modelling (CM) approach	Discrete modelling (DM) approach
Model	Smearred crack model (SCM) Continuum damage mechanics (CDM)	Cohesive interface element Spring element
Overview	The damage is modelled through the constitutive relation. The crack is expressed as the band having the element thickness 	
Advantage	Computational robustness Ability to model the unknown location cracks	Ability to capture stress concentration around the crack tip
Disadvantage	Lack of ability to capture stress concentration around crack tip.	Application is limited for the problem where crack locations are known.
Application	○ Multiple (Diffuse) Crack × Large (Dominant) Crack	○ Large (Dominant) Crack × Multiple (Diffuse) Crack

Figure 6: Schematic figure of numerical damage modeling for advanced composites [6].

Angle-ply laminate

Comparison with FEA results obtained by Gudmundson et al.

- Material : GFRP
- Lay-up configuration : $[\pm 55]_N$, $[\pm 67.5]_N$

Figure 7: Comparison the present model versus finite-element analysis.

2.4 Multiscale bottom-up modeling design of composite aircraft wings.

Most aircraft designs do not consider the microstructure of composite materials but just utilize their homogeneous mechanical properties as an anisotropic body. As stated above, multiscale modeling of composite materials has been fully developed, so that mechanical or strength properties estimated with microstructural properties of CFRP can be directly utilized in such an aircraft design. We developed an aero-structural optimization of a composite aircraft wing considering the microstructure of composite materials, as shown in Figures 8 and 9. Here we will discuss the advantage of using advanced composites versus conventional metals.

Figure 8: Schematic figure of aero-structural optimization of composite aircraft wing.

Figure 9: Schematic diagram of aero-structural optimization of composite aircraft wing based on multiscale modeling.

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